

SPHINX
Site: TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16A2 Locus Number (4)

Progress of Excavation (4) R16A2 cleared w/ trowel Largest limestone pieces resting on or near surface of (4a)

LIMESTONE FRAGS RANGE LARGE TO FINE; LARGEST 24 X 14 X 11

2-3 LARGE ROUNDED PIECES WHITE-SPECKLED GYPSUM

2/II/80 R16A2: Surface (4) (as (3b) cleared) fairly level. Looks same as (3b) matrix. However since no clear demarcation, beginning (4) seems somewhat arbitrary. No stone frags showing scattered carbon flecks. During excavation (4) shows bit more gravelly (limestone chips) than (3b). Also becomes slightly →

Locus Description "BROWN SAND WITH STONE RUBBLE"

In SW corner deposit (see R16-N Balk) more mottled w/ mud flecks and gypsum(?) flecks

Location in Square See Plan

Under Locus (3b) - (3c) Over Locus (4a) COMPACT TAN CLAY

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels 8:43 - 8:36

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Large Frags Granite, Large Frags Limestone, Some large frags Alabaster - 1 Alabaster frag w finished surface, some calcite chips. Few Charcoal spots, 1 large mud spot 1 Large (largest) Granite frag in NE Balk corner may be corner fragment(?)

SHERDS thick CRW, all ND
SOME W SURFACE INDICATE BURNISHED RED WASH

2/II/80 (cont.)

mottled w/ some darker slightly mud-like veins, ^{tan} clay, clean sand spots toward surface of (4a). Stone material after sifting shows fine to small limestone chips w/ some fine granite, dolerite chips included. Larger limestone frags (5-10 cm) (2-3) pick up at surface @ (4a) but in matrix (4). Carbon frags and flecks (small scattered throughout matrix. Shards: only several very small ND frags.